

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF 2-AMINO-4,6-DIARYLPYRIMIDINES (2)^a

Sl. no.	R	X	Mol. formula	M.p. °C	Yield %
1.	Phenyl	Br	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₄ N ₄ Br	205	70
2.	2'-Chlorophenyl	Br	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₄ BrCl	190	75
3.	4'-Chlorophenyl	Br	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₄ BrCl	240	78
4.	2',4'-Dichlorophenyl	Br	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ O ₄ N ₄ BrCl ₂	260	85
5.	4'-Methylphenyl	Br	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ O ₄ N ₄ Br	185	65
6.	3',4'-Methylenedioxyphenyl	Br	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ O ₆ N ₄ Br	162	70
7.	3',4',5'-Trimethoxyphenyl	Br	C ₂₂ H ₂₅ O ₇ N ₄ Br	155	65
8.	3',4'-Dimethoxyphenyl	Br	C ₂₂ H ₂₃ O ₆ N ₄ Br	180	70
9.	4'-Methoxyphenyl	Br	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ O ₅ N ₄ Br	135	65
10.	2'-Methoxyphenyl	Br	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ O ₅ N ₄ Br	201	60
11.	4'-N-Dimethylamino-phenyl	Br	C ₂₃ H ₂₇ O ₄ N ₅ Br	210	62
12.	Phenyl	H	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ O ₄ N ₄	190	70
13.	2'-Bromophenyl	H	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₄ N ₄ Br	235	75
14.	4'-Bromophenyl	H	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₄ N ₄ Br	250	80
15.	2'-Chlorophenyl	H	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₄ N ₄ Cl	202	85
16.	4'-Chlorophenyl	H	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ O ₄ N ₄ Cl	231	80
17.	2',4'-Dichlorophenyl	H	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ O ₄ N ₄ Cl ₂	270	90
18.	2'-Methoxyphenyl	H	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ O ₅ N ₄	185	70
19.	4'-Methoxyphenyl	H	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ O ₅ N ₄	208	65
20.	3',4'-Dimethoxyphenyl	H	C ₂₂ H ₂₄ O ₆ N ₄	160	68
21.	3',4',5'-Trimethoxyphenyl	H	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ O ₇ N ₄	175	70
22.	4'-Methylphenyl	H	C ₂₁ H ₂₃ O ₄ N ₄	198	75
23.	3',4'-Methylenedioxyphenyl	H	C ₂₁ H ₂₁ O ₆ N ₄	217	70
24.	4'-N-Dimethylamino-phenyl	H	C ₂₃ H ₂₇ O ₄ N ₅	165	60

^aAll compounds gave satisfactory N analysis.

(KBr) were taken on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer.

2-Amino-4-(2'-hydroxy-3'-bromo-4'-n-butoxy-5'-nitrophen-1'-yl)-6-phenylpyrimidine (2): A mixture of 2'-hydroxy-3'-bromo-4'-n-butoxy-5'-nitrochalcone (1; X=Br; 1.00 g) and guanidine nitrate (0.30 g) in ethanol (50 ml) was refluxed and an aqueous solution of sodium hydroxide (40%, 5 ml) added to it portionwise during 3 h. The reflux was continued further for 6 h and the resulting solid on cooling was filtered and crystallised from aqueous DMF, (70%), m.p. 205° (Found: C, 52.17; H, 4.21; N, 12.12. C₂₀H₁₉O₄N₄Br calcd. for: C, 52.29; H, 4.14; N, 12.20%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3 460, 3 330 (NH), 1 630 (C=N) and 3 200 cm⁻¹ (OH phenolic).

Similarly, other pyrimidines (Table 1) were prepared.

2-Amino-4-(2'-hydroxy-3'-H-4'-n-butoxy-5'-nitrophen-1'-yl)-6-phenylpyrimidine (2): A mixture of 2'-hydroxy-4-n-butoxy-5'-nitrochalcone (1; X=H, 1.00 g) and guanidine nitrate (0.30 g) in ethanol (50 ml) was refluxed and an aqueous solution of sodium hydroxide (40%; 5 ml) added to it portionwise during 3 h. The reflux was continued further for 8 h and the resulting yellow solid on cooling was filtered and crystallised from aqueous DMF, (75%), m.p. 190° (Found: C, 63.20; H, 5.12; N, 14.82. C₂₀H₂₀O₄N₄ calcd. for: C, 63.16; H, 5.26;

N, 14.74%); $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3 455, 3 335 (NH), 1 620 (C=N) and 3 200 cm⁻¹ (OH phenolic).

Similarly, other pyrimidines (Table 1) were prepared.

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Pyrimidine Antagonists. Part-III. Synthesis of some 2,4-Diamino-5-substituted-phenylazo-6-substituted-aminopyrimidines and Evaluation of their Anticancer Property against Leukemia P388

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PURINE and pyrimidine possess widerange biological activities¹.

The presence of amino groups in C-2 and C-4 positions of the pyrimidine ring and also the presence of hydroxyl and/or amino groups in C-2 and C-4 positions having a bulky substituted-amino group in C-6 position² have been found to exhibit activity against *Streptococcus faecalis* ATCC 8043. The present investigation aims to keep the 2,4-diaminopyrimidine moiety intact and then substitute new group at the phenylmoiety at the C-6 position having phenylazo group in C-5 position.

In previous communications³ the present author reported the synthesis of some 2,4-diamino-6-substituted-aminopyrimidines and 2,4-diamino-6-substituted-amino-5-arylazopyrimidines.

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NOTES

The new 5-phenylazopyrimidines (2) were synthesised by the reaction of an appropriate 2,4-diamino-6-substituted-aminopyrimidine (1) with diazotised phenylamine at 0–10° and pH 3–4 or 5–7 or 8–9 depending on the nature of 1 used. The 5-phenylazopyrimidines (2; Table 1) were found to be soluble in ethanol, methanol, acetone, pyridine and ethyl acetate but insoluble in benzene and toluene at room temperature.

Some of the compounds were screened for their anticancer activity against mouse Leukemia P388 at National Cancer Institute, U.S.A.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in capillary tubes on a aluminium block. M.p. of the compounds that melted with decomposition was determined by rapidly heating the block to 20° below the actual m.p. and subsequently at the rate of 4°/min. All the m.ps. are uncorrected. Absorption spectra of the compound were determined in a Shimadzu 210A spectrophotometer and ir spectra (KBr) in a Perkin-Elmer 1310B spectrophotometer.

General methods of preparation of 5-phenylazopyrimidines (2): To a suspension of 2,4,6-trisubstituted-pyrimidine^s (0.004 mol) in water (200 ml), glacial acetic acid (10–20 ml) was added dropwise with stirring until a clear solution was obtained. 2,4-Diamino-6-*p*-sulphoanilinopyrimidine and 2,4-diamino-6-*p*-carboxyanilinopyrimidine were dissolved in 10 *N* NaOH (10 ml) and 2,4-diamino-6-*p*-nitroanilinopyrimidine was dissolved in 10 *N* HCl (10 ml). The solution was cooled in ice-water and a ice-cold solution of an equimolar amount of the diazotised arylamine (prepared by adding a cold solution of 0.004 mol NaNO₂ in 10 ml water with stirring to an ice-cold solution of 0.004 mol amine in 20 ml 1 *N* HCl; the diazotised solution containing excess of HCl) was added slowly with stirring (5 min). Then 1 *N* NaOH solution was added to it dropwise to bring pH of the solution to 8–9 when precipitate of 2 (sl. nos. 1, 8 and 22) appeared. Stirring was continued for 4 h. In case of compounds 2 (sl. nos. 2, 4, 9, 11, 18, 23 and 25) the solution

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF 5-PHENYLAZOPYRIMIDINES (2)*

Sl. no.	R ₁	R ₂	Mol. formula	Yield %	Colour nature	M.p.** °C	λ _{max} † nm	ν _{max} cm ⁻¹
1.	OC ₂ H ₅	OH ₂	C ₁₉ H ₂₂ N ₇ O	95	Brownish yellow crystal	210 ^a	389s, 395, 425	1 430, 1 890 (OH ₂), 2 920 (OH aliph), 1 116 (OC ₂ H ₅)
2.	COOH	OH ₂	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ N ₇ O ₃	80	Reddish brown crystal	340d ^c	305s, 400, 430, 485i	1 430, 1 880 (OH ₂), 2 920 (OH aliph), 2 760 (COOH), 1 715 (CO)
3.	SO ₂ NH ₂	OH ₂	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₇ O ₂	60	Canary yellow plate	198d ^b	300s, 350, 390, 430, 485	1 430 (OH ₂), 2 920 (OH aliph), 1 160, 1 320 (SO ₂ NH ₂)
4.	SO ₂ H	CH ₃	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₇ SO ₂	98	Reddish brown crystal	278–82 ^a	303s, 385, 485	1 460 (OH ₂), 2 920 (OH aliph), 1 170, 1 030, 650 (SO ₂ H)
5.	NO ₂	OH ₂	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₇ O ₂	70	Snuff crystal	250d ^b	260, 308vi, 380, 485i	1 450, 1 890 (OH ₂), 2 920 (OH aliph), 1 500, 1 800 (NO ₂)
6.	Br	OH ₂	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ BrN ₇	80	Yellowish brown crystal	180 ^a	345s, 400, 422i	1 450, 1 870 (CH ₂), 2 910 (OH aliph), 510 (Br)
7.	Cl	OH ₂	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ ClN ₇	90	Yellow shining needle	260–67d ^b	290s, 394, 430, 485	1 450, 1 380 (OH ₂), 1 830 (OH bend), 780 (Cl)
8.	OC ₂ H ₅	SO ₂ NH ₂	C ₁₉ H ₂₁ N ₇ SO ₂	98	Orange crystal	170 ^a	280s, 420i, 485	1 150, 1 340 (SO ₂ NH ₂), 1 100 (OC ₂ H ₅)

(Table 1 contd.)

9.	COOH	SO ₂ NH ₂	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₃ SO ₂	98	Reddish brown crystal	300 ^d	260, 420, 440	1 150, 1 330 (SO ₂ NH), 2 920 (COOH), 1 690 (OO)
10.	SO ₂ NH ₂	SO ₂ NH ₂	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₃ S ₂ O ₂	90	Orange shining plate	217d ^a	295s, 405i, 435	1 160, 1 320, 1 340 (SO ₂ NH)
11.	SO ₂ H	SO ₂ NH ₂	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ N ₃ S ₂ O ₂	90	Light yellow crystal	305d ^a	355i, 406, 425	1 150, 1 320 (SO ₂ NH), 1 150, 1 020, 640 (SO ₂ H)
12.	NO ₂	SO ₂ NH ₂	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₃ SO ₂	98	Yellowish orange shining needle	162 ^b	260, 320vi, 396, 485	1 180, 1 340 (SO ₂ NH), 1 505, 1 300 (NO ₂)
13.	Br	SO ₂ NH ₂	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ BrN ₃ SO ₂	95	Brownish yellow shining crystal	245 ^b	293, 350i, 398, 430, 485	1 160, 1 340 (SO ₂ NH), 620 (Br)
14.	Cl	SO ₂ NH ₂	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ ClN ₃ S ₂ O ₂	90	Light brownish yellow crystal	305 ^c	295s, 380, 430, 485i	1 160, 1 350 (SO ₂ NH), 800 (Cl)
15.	OC ₂ H ₅	SO ₂ H	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ N ₃ SO ₂	95	Orange crystal	260 ^b	260s, 355s, 390	1 170, 1 050, 650 (SO ₂ H), 1 125 (OC ₂ H ₅)
16.	COOH	SO ₂ H	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₃ SO ₂	45	Brown crystal	280 ^a	260, 304s, 409br, 485i	1 170, 1 030, 640 (SO ₂ H), 2 925 (COOH), 1 680 (OO)
17.	SO ₂ NH ₂	SO ₂ H	C ₁₆ H ₁₇ N ₃ S ₂ O ₂ [†]	88	Canary yellow crystal	290-97 ^b	295s, 410i, 430	1 150, 1 030, 650 (SO ₂ H), 1 150, 1 325 (SO ₂ NH)
18.	SO ₂ H	SO ₂ H	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₃ S ₂ O ₂	10	Brown powder	240 ^b	285s, 315vi, 370br	1 180, 1 040, 650 (SO ₂ H)
19.	NO ₂	SO ₂ H	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₃ SO ₂	98	Brownish yellow shining crystal	190 ^b	265, 385, 485i	1 190, 1 020, 640 (SO ₂ H), 1 520, 1 310 (NO ₂)
20.	Br	SO ₂ H	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ BrN ₃ SO ₂	80	Canary yellow plate	260d ^a	291s, 340, 400, 430, 485i	1 200, 1 040, 640 (SO ₂ H), 580 (Br)
21.	Cl	SO ₂ H	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ ClN ₃ SO ₂	98	Yellow shining plate	265 ^b	287s, 340vi, 400, 430	1 210, 1 030 (SO ₂ H), 800 (Cl)
22.	OC ₂ H ₅	NO ₂	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₂	99	Reddish brown crystal	240 ^a	255, 335s, 385	1 570, 1 370, 1 300 (NO ₂), 1 150, 1 100 (OC ₂ H ₅)
23.	COOH	NO ₂	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₃ O ₂	99	Orange shining needle	270 ^a	255, 290, 450	1 560, 1 320 (NO ₂), 2 930 (COOH), 1 680 (OO)
24.	SO ₂ NH ₂	NO ₂	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₃ SO ₂	97	Orange red shining needle	200 ^a	295, 401s, 460vi	1 560, 1 340 (NO ₂), 1 160, 1 310 (SO ₂ NH)
25.	SO ₂ H	NO ₂	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₃ SO ₂	40	Reddish brown crystal	275d ^a	270, 320vi, 400	1 500, 1 340 (NO ₂), 1 150, 1 070, 625 (SO ₂ H)
26.	NO ₂	NO ₂	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₃ O ₂	90	Light brownish yellow needle	232-36d ^a	270, 320vi, 400s	1 500, 1 360, 1 340 (NO ₂)
27.	Br	NO ₂	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ BrN ₃ O ₂	98	Chocolate red shining crystal	198 ^a	282, 400s, 485i	1 560, 1 340, 1 300 (NO ₂), 530 (Br)
28.	Cl	NO ₂	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ ClN ₃ O ₂	99	Blood red crystal	205-10d ^b	296, 397, 467i, 485	1 510, 1 350 (NO ₂), 800 (Cl)

*All compounds furnished satisfactory C, H and N analyses. **Solvent for crystallisation: ^aethanol, ^baqueous ethanol, ^cpyridine, ^daqueous pyridine.
[†]s=sharp; br=broad, i=inconspicuous, vi=very inconspicuous.

became coloured instead of giving precipitate. In such cases after stirring for 4 h, pH was adjusted to 3–4 by adding 1 N HCl to get precipitate. In case of 2 (sl. no. 16) pH was maintained at 3–4 by adding 1 N HCl and stirring continued for 4 h, the solution then became coloured instead of giving precipitate, pH was adjusted to 8–9 by 1 N NaOH when precipitate appeared. The pH was adjusted to 3–4 for 2 (sl. nos. 13, 14, 17, 19, 24, 26) and 8–9 for 2 (sl. nos. 5 and 12) by 2 N HCl or 2 N NaOH and stirring continued for 4 h when heavy precipitate appeared for 2 (sl. nos. 5, 12, 24 and 26). For compounds 2 (sl. nos. 13, 14, 17 and 19) pH was maintained at 8–9 by 2 N NaOH to get heavy precipitate. In case of 2 (sl. nos. 3, 6, 7, 10, 15, 20, 21, 27 and 28) pH was adjusted to 6–7 by adding 2 N HCl or 2 N NaOH and stirring was continued for 4 h to get precipitate. Low temperature (0–10°) was maintained throughout the reaction. The mixture was kept in a refrigerator for 12 h and the crude product filtered, washed several times with water, dried (80°) and crystallised.

Anticancer activity: Some of the compounds (2) were screened for their anticancer activity against mouse Leukemia P388. The vehicle used was saline or saline with Tween 80 which gave a smooth suspension (homogeneous or cloudy mixture) depending on the dose employed and the nature of the compound. The mixture was then injected in the penecrious of a male mouse and the activity compared with the control. Surviving animals/total animals on toxicity evaluation day was taken into count. Animal body-weight difference was computed by subtracting the control group body-weight changes from that of the test group.

The test evaluation expressed as a percent of the control evaluation, provided a measure of effectiveness of the compound being tested. Survival system indicates a degree of success when test/control (T/C) percent ≥ 120 . However, maximum T/C values were obtained for the compound having sl. no. 20, i.e. 122 at dose level of 50 mg/kg, 121 at 100 mg/kg and 114 at 200 mg/kg. The other compounds having sl. nos. 3–5, 8–12, 15, 17, 19, 20, 22, 24–26 were found to have T/C values in the range 86–113 at the dose level tested (50–400 mg/kg).

The phenylazopyrimidines having an arylamino group at C-6 showed a strong absorption band in the region 274–292 nm and those having saturated substituted-amino group at C-6 showed at 240–275 nm. All the compounds, however, exhibited an additional high intensity band at 386–442 nm, being responsible for their colour.

The ir spectra for all the compounds revealed identical bands at 3 500–3 300 (NH), 1 690–1 640 (C=N, pyrimidine), 1 630–1 575 (N=N), 1 667–1 429 (C=C Ar, four bands), 1 360–1 250 (CN amines) and 680–780 cm^{-1} (ν subs. benz.), confirming that the compounds are identical in

nature. But the representative compounds showed different signals due to the presence of substituted group in the aromatic ring, whose assignments are presented in Table 1.

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